

THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN FLIPPED LEARNING AND TRADITIONAL LEARNING

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Abstract

The Flipped Classroom is an innovative learning scenario that has gained wide popularity due to the power of digital tools. Its difference from the traditional scenario lies in the fact that the theoretical material is studied independently before the start of the lesson (as a rule, through information and communication technologies: video lectures, audio lectures, interactive materials, etc.), and the freed up time in the lesson is aimed at solving problems, collaboration, interaction with students, application of knowledge.

Keywords: flipped learning, difference in learning, learning strategy.

The main advantage of the flipped classroom lies in the organization of the study with which:

- supporting the development of 21st century qualities and skills such as collaboration, creativity, problem solving, self-reliance, ICT literacy, etc.;
- and provides an opportunity to support the development of each student.

The inverted class differs from the traditional class in that the teacher has releases during the lesson: time for contact and individual work with students. This is achieved through the organization of joint work of students and appropriate educational materials, allowing the workers to work independently and autonomously. When working collaboratively, students are free to help each other depending on the pace of other students or the teacher's instructions. And the teacher has opportunity to work with students one-on-one.

Organized work in this way changes the usual roles of both the teacher and the student. And such changes, alas, are not easy for both the first and second.

With a flipped classroom, the teacher ceases to be the central figure in the educational process, which is perceived by teachers as a loss of status. And students for many school years have become accustomed to a passive role in the educational process. The flipped classroom model is a type of blended learning. A flipped classroom (lesson) is a teaching model in which the teacher provides material for self-study at home, and in the face-to-face lesson, there is a practical consolidation of the material. Flipped learning is characterized by the use of vodcasts, podcasts, and pre-vodcasting. Before getting into the details, let's understand the key concepts.

A podcast is a sound file (audio lecture) that its creator sends by subscription via the Internet. Recipients can download podcasts to their devices, both fixed and mobile, or listen to lectures online. Vodcast (Vodcast from video-on-demand, i.e. video on demand) is about the same as a podcast, only with video files. Pre-vodcasting is an educational method in which a school teacher or university professor creates a vodcast of his lecture so that students get an idea of a topic even before the lesson in which this topic will be considered.

The pre-casting method is the original name of the inverted class method. As a result, the attitude towards independent activity gradually becomes pragmatic and formal.

Let's compare the traditional and "flipped" approaches to learning according to several criteria: the role of the student, the role of the teacher, the role of ICT in the educational process, the methods used and building a lesson.

To avoid a number of problems associated with the "coup", the transition from the traditional class to the inverted one is carried out gradually. It is important for the teacher to understand that his role is to "give a lesson", to convey and then to test knowledge. Its role is to create a learning situation for independent cognitive and research activities of students. Ta situations in which they will be responsible for their own learning. Here then also it is possible to consider that the class is turned over.

There is a technology for using vodcasts in the educational process using special software:

CMS (Content Management System, content management system) - used to create and manage the content of educational materials;

LMS (Learning Management System, distance learning system) - provides access to educational materials, organization of feedback and horizontal links, etc.

An example of a vodcast created in iSpring Suite:

The Flipped Class is a learning model in which doing homework includes, among other things, the use of vodcast technologies:

- watching a video lecture;
- reading educational texts, viewing explanatory drawings;
- passing tests for the initial assimilation of the topic. Class work is devoted to the analysis of a complex theoretical part and questions that arose in students in the process of doing homework (no more than 25-30% of the time). Also in the classroom, students under the supervision of a teacher solve practical problems and perform research tasks. After classes in the classroom at home, practical tasks are completed, tests are

performed to understand and consolidate the topic covered. The transition to the flipped classroom model is a transition from teacher-led to student-led. In foreign literature, this transition is figuratively described as a change in the role of a teacher from “sage on the stage” to “guide on the side”, which can be loosely translated as a transition from “a wise man and a player on the pipe” to “a guide - from the side he steers”.

How modern technology has affected flipped learning. The founders of the flipped classroom model are considered to be two teachers, Jonathon Bergman and Aaron Sams, who in 2007 first figured out how to provide their lectures to athletes who often skip classes, and then developed this idea into a new educational direction. In this they were helped by publications in major American newspapers and magazines. In particular, in the Times magazine of December 10, 2006, in the article “How to Pull Our Schools Out of the 20th Century,” we read: “American schools are certainly not frozen in time, but given the pace of change in other areas of life, our public schools are becoming something like a relic of the past. Children spend most of the day the way their great-grandparents once did: sitting in rows listening to a teacher lecture, hand-scribbling scribbles in notebooks, and reading textbooks that are outdated the day they go out of print.”

Bergman recalls: “In the spring of 2007, Aaron showed me an article about a software product that allows you to create a slideshow in PowerPoint that includes voice and any text notes. The whole thing is then converted into a video file that is easy to distribute online. We realized that this could allow our students to skip classes without missing out on learning! We have started posting our lectures online for students to access. To be honest, we recorded our lectures for selfish reasons. We spent an unreasonable amount of time arranging follow-up sessions for students who missed classes. The lecture notes became our first line of defense.” We don't know if iSpring inspired this idea way back in 2007, but today, in 2023, flipped learning with direct YouTube video upload is available in the iSpring Suite.

The flipped classroom model is sometimes blamed for weakening the role of the teacher. In fact, the transition to this model opens the way to increasing the importance of the role of the teacher in learning. The teacher can spend the time freed up due to pre-casting on more complex professional tasks - consolidating and deepening the knowledge gained by students on their own.

The flipped classroom is often confused with distance education. The difference lies on the surface - the

time of classroom work “face to face” remains unchanged, only its content changes fundamentally.

Other critics of the flipped classroom argue that the model degrades the traditional aspect of education by not being able to promptly ask the lecturer questions. Defenders of the model respond that the need for such questions is reduced by additional features that appear when using LMS:

- an incomprehensible place of the video lecture can be reviewed as many times as you like; you can refer to the FAQ (frequently asked questions); you can ask questions to other students using the discussion module in the LMS (here, the mechanisms of the social theory of knowledge are additionally included);

- you can send questions to the teacher via the built-in email to get clarifications in the upcoming class session.

Nowadays, the vast majority of students are fond of receiving various information by holding a mobile phone. It is not surprising that effective education has a new format depending on the taste of students. A student with well-developed theoretical knowledge can also pay attention to practice and do various laboratory or research work without any obstacles. By studying the effective teaching system, teaching increases students' desire to learn. It seems that the flipped learning system is an effective way for students to acquire theoretical knowledge. In the process of mastering new material using FC teaching technology, the indicator of the quality of students' education was 69%.

Summarizing the research, it can be seen that this technology is effective in improving the quality of education

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